

Visiting the Margins
INnovative **CUL**tural **ToURisM** in European peripheries

Mining treasures of Central Slovakia

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**BANÍCKE
POKLADY**

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CONTEXT

The pilot is located in the Banská Bystrica self-government region which is the largest of eight regions (NUTS 3 level) in Slovakia that covers an area of 9 454 km². It has a population of approximately 626 thousand people with a population density of less than 70 inhabitants per 1 km². It is a very heterogeneous region in terms of economic and social structure as well as geography, but generally consists of a mountainous and better-

developed north and a flat and agrarian south, bordering with Hungary. The unemployment rate in the region is higher than the average of the country (5.9 %) on the level of 8.48% (in December 2022), with the unemployment rate ranging from 3,9 % in Banská Bystrica district to close to 20% in Rimavská Sobota district. However, this region has a significant cultural and technical heritage related to its mining history, which is not fully exploited and has a high potential for development. The development and promotion of cultural and creative tourism can help rural and remote areas in this region to increase sustainable job opportunities and investments. The Historic Town of Banská Štiavnica, and the Technical Monuments in its Vicinity (from 1993 enlisted at the UNESCO World Heritage List), are outstanding examples of an important mining settlement that has developed since the Middle Ages. The city of Banská Bystrica is the cultural and economic centre of Central Slovakia. The copper mining city acquired its present picturesque look in the Late Middle Ages when the affluent Fugger and Thurzo families founded the prosperous, largest and most modern early-capitalist company of that time. Depending mainly on the mines around Banská Bystrica, the company became the leading world producer of copper by the 16th century. Several other localities in the region were part of this important mining history while preserving cultural and technical heritage of international relevance.

The pilot project is also a cross-cutting action within two tourist routes – the Barbora Route and the European Fugger Route. The Barbora Route passes through the most significant mining sites and monuments associated with the mining tradition throughout the region of the former Central Slovak mining towns. The European Fugger Route (Fuggerstrasse) takes visitors to silver and copper mines in Austria, Germany, Italy and Slovakia, where the Fugger family made their fortune. Despite the fact, that the Banská Bystrica region owns the great potential of this heritage for tourism and plays an important role in both routes (Barbora Route and Fugger Route), its development is vastly underrated in the region and cities and region significantly lacks marketing and digital tools promoting this unique part of its history.

OBJECTIVES OF THE PILOT PROJECT “MINING TREASURES OF CENTRAL SLOVAKIA”

In this context, the pilot project is aimed at creating an interactive digital platform about mining treasures in mining towns in central Slovakia, which intersects two tourist routes in the northern part of the Banská Bystrica self-governing region in central Slovakia, including the mining towns of Banská Bystrica and Banská Štiavnica (UNESCO World Heritage Site). The most important mining locations are presented on one responsive platform and a digital map available as a software application called "Mining Treasures". In the phase of its design, creation, testing and marketing, researchers, students, partners and the general public are involved.

Mining treasures of Central Slovakia pursues 4 main objectives:

1. The participatory creation of a responsive web platform *Mining treasures (Banícke poklady)* including digital map on mining treasures in Central Slovakia.
2. Contribute to the creation of awareness about importance and significance of the cultural heritage associated with mining in central Slovakia and participate in building a mining heritage community in Slovakia.
3. To project the results and outputs of pilot action into education.
4. To help build sustainable tourism and tourism sustainability through the platform Mining treasures that promotes even hitherto unknown locations for tourists.

INNOVATIONS OF THE PILOT ACTION “MINING TREASURES OF CENTRAL SLOVAKIA”

In this information sheet, we propose to review the main innovations developed within the Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia.

Technical and product innovations (hard innovations)	Social innovations (soft innovations)
Technical part of the pilot action connected with participatory approach of content and design creation.	In education and learning through the creation of unique educational content with a potential to lead into change in curricula.
	Networking, cooperation and participation of wide network of stakeholders (from public, private and non-profit sector) and individuals.
Responsive web platform created by using participatory approach which is a unique product of cultural tourism with educational context.	Robust and unique presentation of mining heritage (tangible, intangible, industrial) including localities that were until now out of tourist interest.
	Empowering the creation of mining heritage community
	Enhancing development of cultural tourism respecting both tourism sustainability and sustainable tourism

Above mentioned innovations are achieved through the activities implemented within the INCULTUM project and its pilot action Mining treasures of central Slovakia.

ACTIONS OF THE PILOT PROJECT "MINING TREASURES OF CENTRAL SLOVAKIA"

The pilot project achieves the stated objectives through activities:

1. Data collection (text, photograph, maps, GPS...)
2. Meetings with communities
3. Creation and design of responsive platform – technical part
4. Creation and design of responsive platform – design and marketing part – logo competition, participatory approach to logo design and creation
5. Creation of content for responsive platform – participatory approach to platform content development

Data collection

As part of the pilot project "Mining treasures of Central Slovakia", we collect and evaluate primary and secondary data related to the creation of an interactive platform, testing, use and promotion of the platform, as well as general information from the field of tourism in the Banská Bystrica region.

Data related to the creation of the interactive platform:

- Collection of secondary data related to the content of the interactive platform; this includes texts, photographs, video, and audio materials.
- Collection or creation of primary data related to the content of interactive platform; this includes texts, photographs, video, and audio materials

Data related to the testing, use and promotion of the interactive platform:

- Collection of data related to testing and usage of the platform, such as number of visits/clicks, number of interactions, and data related to feedback while using the interactive platform (from local communities and beyond).
- Collection of data related to using/promoting the platform and its content through social media (e.g., using the hashtag #banickepoklady / #miningtreasures, liking, commenting, sharing the content of the platform through different types of social media).
- Collection of data related to the deployment of the mystery shopping model by testing the interactive platform.

General information from the field of tourism in the Banská Bystrica region:

- Collecting primary or secondary data related to the utilization of the platform and its promotion through social media (e.g., using the hashtag #banickepoklady / #miningtreasures, liking, commenting, sharing the content of the platform through different types of social media)
- Collection of primary or secondary data related to activities related to the use of the platform (e.g. possible entrepreneurial activities supported by the existence of the platform, the flow of tourists heading the 'newly' promoted places through the platform, such as visits of industrial heritage, mid-term/long-term changes in the structure of the tourist and/or tourism industry in the region)

Interesting facts :

- Physical visits of more than: **30 museums, 60 tangible heritage objects, 40 industrial heritage objects, 25 events**
- More than **250 texts** prepared and reviewed for the content of the interactive platform
- More than **2 300 photos** taken
- More than **350 websites** visited to get inspired
- More than **100 people** participated in data

Challenges and further steps:

We plan to include the third mining city in Central Slovakia—Kremnica—thereby enriching the platform with new and original content.

We plan to design a physical map that includes a layer capable of interconnecting with the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" platform by special application

Meeting with communities

At the very beginning of the project, we realised several important meetings with key stakeholders for the implementation of our pilot Mining treasures of Central Slovakia. This includes Regional Destination Management Organisation BBSK, Local Destination Management Organisation Banská Štiavnica and the Local Destination Management Organisation Central Slovakia. We enhanced the participation of students who become active contributors to the platform through creating original content for the platform. Additionally, we had more than twenty meetings with ICT company related to the preparation phase of the interactive digital platform. We also received training for interactive platform content functionalities and adding of items by the company which is designing the interactive platform.

We organized several field trips into main localities related to mining treasures of Central Slovakia, namely to Banska Štiavnica, Špania Dolina and Banská Bystrica.

Through destination management organisations and numerous meetings with local organisation we include new groups of local communities and individuals into the pilot action implementation. We successfully involved local photographers whose provide photos and visual materials for the content of the platform.

University students are involved through the whole pilot action implementation through specific assignments in five different courses (Creativity and culture in regional development, New trends in local and regional policy, Participatory public policy making, Basics of marketing and Marketing of public and non-profit sector). Participation of students led to the creation of 19 proposals for the logo and design manual of the interactive mining

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treasures platform. The winning proposal is used in the final version of the platform (also included in this Factsheet). Students also become active contributors and users of the platform. At the beginning of 2023, we met with the author of a children's book called "Copper Land", which tells the story of the Špania Dolina treasure and how a forest elf became a permonian. We were also invited to a book launch and start collaboration with this author.

In 2023, there was also an opportunity to meet and establish collaboration with stakeholders significantly engaged in safeguarding and enhancing the mining heritage for sustainable tourism and the innovation of new products. These stakeholders included CA Terra Montanae, CA Štiavnický tajch, Maxilian Hella Štiavnické Bane Primary School with Kindergarten, CA Špaňodolinská Historical School, and the Slovak Mining Museum in Banská Štiavnica. Particularly close collaboration was fostered with CA Terra Montanae, overseeing the Barbora Route project. Subsequently, in August 2023, a Memorandum of Cooperation was signed with CA Terra Montanae representatives, not only concerning the establishment of an interactive platform.

There was excellent cooperation in developing the interactive platform with CA Štiavnický Tajch. This organisation, along with its dedicated volunteers, actively participates in revitalising the Banská Štiavnica water management system, which remains the most significant water management structure ever built in Slovakia.

On April 25th, we organised in the city of Banská Bystrica the conference dedicated to

Interesting facts:

The following individuals and organisations are involved so far:

- More than **50 organisation** from public, private and non-profit sector
- More than **90 students** from **5 academic courses**
- **29 photographers** (4 of them professional)
- **25 active authors** of the content of the interactive platform
- with whom we realised more than **45**

the mining cultural heritage of Central Slovakia.

The goal of the conference was to present the mining heritage of central Slovakia, with a focus on the Barbora route, to exchange knowledge and experience from the development of mining cultural routes in Europe with members of Mines B. – European Mining Routes of Santa Barbara Federation

and beyond, and to strengthen the creation of networks between various interested parties to support the use of the participatory platform Mining Treasures. A total of four main speakers presented at the conference, who, in addition to introducing the INCULTUM project and the pilot project Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia, also discussed the possibilities of using participatory methods and models in cultural tourism, as well as the opportunities of utilizing cultural tourist routes in the development of territories. Subsequently, a panel discussion was held with members of Mines B., which brought forth a wealth of interesting information and ideas related to the existence and development of mining cultural routes across Europe. The event also featured the official opening of a

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traveling exhibition dedicated to women and men in mining After the official part of the conference at the Town Hall, the participants moved to the premises of Matej's House, where they were introduced to the rich mining history of the central Slovakia region in the Thurzo – Fugger Interactive Exhibition.

The conference was attended by over 100 participants from various sectors, including public, private, and non-profit, all sharing an interest in the mining cultural heritage of Central Slovakia. The conference thus created not only fertile ground for discussion but also for building a community dedicated to cultural heritage.

Creation and design of responsive platform - technical part

Challenges and further steps:

We are scheduling a series of meetings with representatives from non-profit organisations, as well as numerous sessions with students and educators. These meetings aim to advance the creation of distinctive educational content that will be integrated into the platform.

The development of the platform is carried out in three main phases as follows:

Phase 1 Information architecture/web design/development

(Based on the specified requirements, the information architecture of the interactive platform was developed, followed by the design the necessary subpages, modules and elements, and deploy the front-end and back-end).

Phase 2 Integration / Framework / SEO / Training

Integration of a new visual identity and design modifications Deploying demo content - Activities, articles, static pages SEO Preparation of the content framework for preparation Document with manual Cloud content architecture Two-phase training in working with the content framework and deploying content via TYPO 3.

Phase 3 Back-end configuration / implementation

Configuration of content management system for language mutations Configuration of recording elements for translation (activities, articles, tags, etc.). Route interconnection configuration Google Analytics Configuration testing Creating language files with a list of static texts / expressions for translation Implementation of texts from language files Additional filters (route complexity, or other parameter).

When creating the content of the platform, we work with the designed TYPO 3 system, through which we insert texts, images, videos, names of the authors and photographs and tags onto the platform.

The participatory creation of the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" platform commenced in June 2021. In addition to web designers, researchers involved in the project and students participated in the design of the responsive platform. The result of joint work is a digital interactive platform of the Mining treasures of central Slovakia is composed of several components that are precisely described in Annex 1 of this Factsheet. The final user version of the platform was launched in December 2022. Also since April 2023, an English version has been available. The Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia platform is accessible at www.banickepoklady.eu. Detailed instructions for using the Mining Treasures of Central

Challenges and further steps:

In the future, we are considering supplementing the interactive platform with other modules that would bring even more interaction to the platform visitor (for example, educational games, competitions, audio stories for the little ones, etc.)

Slovakia platform are available directly on the platform in the part "Articles" – "Manual for working with the platform Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia".

Creation and design of responsive platform – design and marketing part – logo competition, participatory approach to logo design and creation

Students in the courses Basics of marketing and Marketing of public and non-profit sector were actively involved in the creation of the design of the interactive platform through the specific assignment related with the visual identity of the platform. Participation in the creation of the visual identity for the mining treasures platform was realized in the participatory way through the logo competition in which a total of 31 students were involved. Participation of students on this competition led to the creation of 19 proposals for the visual identity, logo and design manual of the interactive mining treasures platform. Numerous interesting and relevant proposals for the logo was received, and thus it was quite challenging to choose the winning logo that will represent the Mining treasures of central Slovakia. Which one would you choose?

The winning logo design is:

The logotype consists of the abstract symbolism of mining - a hammer, which is interspersed with a cross as a sign used in the context of marking a place, a goal... (treasure). The logotype as a whole thus refers to the discovery and wandering of "mining treasures".

The winning logo design was modified by the designers into the final form that we use on the platform, social media, in presentations, materials and documents. The winning logo was embedded with a pin symbol, which we use to indicate activity on the platform map. The pin sign also appeared in other logo designs from students.

Over 40 additional students from the Creativity and Culture in Regional Development course contributed to promoting the platform by sharing posts on social networks such as Facebook and Instagram, using the hashtag #banickepoklady. These posts primarily feature photos from their visits to platform activities, including galleries, museums, monuments, events, and more.

Interesting facts about the visual identity of mining treasures:

- 19 unique logo proposals for "Mining treasures of central Slovakia"
- 31 students involved from 2 academic courses
- Very difficult to choose just winning logo!
- 3 social media profiles (Facebook, Instagram, YouTube) created

Challenges and further steps:

We want to involve other students in the marketing part of creating a responsive platform, who will create short trailers for the platform and activities of Mining Treasures. Similarly, we would like to involve the general public (collecting of old photos, poems, stories) and thus to empower creating of a mining heritage community.

Creation of content for responsive platform – participatory approach to platform content

Creating the content of an interactive platform is a rather demanding process, which includes: preparation of text obtained from several sources (books, articles, websites, meetings with the community), photography and editing of photos, obtaining information about entrance, opening hours, time required, track length, restrictions. Furthermore, it is necessary to obtain the exact location using Google Maps and the coordinates, which must be verified directly in the field. The content of the interactive platform is created in a participatory manner with the involvement of students, representatives of partner organizations and scientists involved in the project. In this way, a total of 18 students from the Creativity and Culture in Regional Development course were involved in the creation of the content of the interactive platform, who had the task of visiting selected activities of the Mining treasures of central Slovakia (museums and galleries, material monuments, industrial monuments) and processing the content of the interactive platform. The result of their work presents Annex 2.

Interesting facts about the content development:

- **25 authors** who actively created content for the platform involved so far
- more than **250 activities** for mining treasures platform created so far
- **18 students** involved who completed a total of 54 activities

Challenges and further steps:
 We plan to include the third mining city in Central Slovakia—Kremnica and educational category —thereby enriching the platform with new and original content. We want to process the content for approximately 500 mining treasure activities in central Slovakia, with a focus on lesser-known, but nevertheless historically significant, Mining treasures in central Slovakia.

SUMMARY OF PRELIMINARY RESULTS OF THE PILOT PROJECT “MINING TREASURES OF CENTRAL SLOVAKIA”

The pilot project has achieved interesting results so far:

Indicator	Value
Number of individuals, organisations and communities involved in the project	50+
Number of meetings with partners	45
Total number of students involved in the project	90

Indicator	Value
Number of students involved in creating the content of the Mining treasures website	18
Number of activities processed by students on the Mining treasures website	54
Number of students involved in the creation of the Mining treasures logo	31
Number of Mining treasures logo designs	19
Number of study subjects in which students participated in the project	5
Number of activities on the website Mining treasures	250
Number of photographers involved in the creation of web content	29
Number of authors involved in the creation of web content	25
Number of social media platforms involved (Facebook, Instagram, YouTube)	3
Number of users of the platform	1000+

CHALLENGES OF THE PILOT PROJECT "MINING TREASURES OF CENTRAL SLOVAKIA"

Despite the numerous activities that we implemented as part of the project, we are aware of the emerging challenges for the future. We aim to address these challenges in subsequent project funded through the Matching Grants call, leveraging resources obtained under the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programs:

- Implementation of project activities and innovations also for the city of Kremnica, which, like the cities of Banská Bystrica and Banská Štiavnica in the past, played an important role in this mining region in the context of "copper" Banská Bystrica, "silver" Banská Štiavnica and "golden" Kremnica. The city of Kremnica is also located on both tourist routes – the Barbora Route and the European Fugger Route. In addition to its rich cultural-historical (mining) heritage (UNESCO World Heritage Site), Kremnica is known for the oldest mint in the world.
- Creation of an original prototype of a physical map of central Slovakia and/or the Barborská cesta, which will include an original layer that enables connection with the application that will integrate the content of the www.banickepoklady.eu platform.
- Creation, development and design of an original application that will enable the connection between the traditional discovery of locations in the form of a map and digital discovery through the application. The application will make it possible to connect the physical map with the www.banickepoklady.eu platform.
- Organising an Idea-Hackathon: This event, centred on innovation and technology, will offer a platform for fostering creative thinking and the development of new products and services within the tourism sector and related fields. The Idea-Hackathon will enable participants from diverse industries to collaborate on tackling specific challenges and devising innovative solutions for the region, in alignment with the Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia project.
- Targeted events tailored for young individuals to encourage their active engagement. A workshop will be held within the Entrepreneurship Academy, and another at the SPACE Youth Work Center, in collaboration with BBSK and the BBSK Development Agency. These workshops will emphasize education and the enhancement of business and professional skills. At the Entrepreneurship Academy,

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participants will have the chance to refine their business concepts and receive invaluable guidance from seasoned mentors. Meanwhile, the workshop at the SPACE Youth Work Center will provide young individuals with opportunities to develop skills essential for their career advancement and active involvement in the community.

- Developing digital content for the "Education" category on the banickepoklady.eu platform in Slovak and English. This content will encompass text documents, photographs, audio-visual materials, and interactive contests.
- Crafting a compelling and unique selection of educational activities in collaboration with local partners.
- Implementation of competitions for schools, including: art competitions, literary competitions, educational competitions and others.
- Creation of the educational game Mining treasures
- Implementation of competitions for the mining community and the general public through social media
- Creating a children's book about mining treasures, in a participatory way.

References

Annex 1

Components of Mining Treasures responsive platform

The main menu bar contains activities, routes, the city of Banská Bystrica and the city of Banská Štiavnica.

Via the **social media menu**, the visitor of the interactive platform can link to the profiles of "Mining treasures of central Slovakia" on the Facebook, Instagram and YouTube platforms.

Icon for direct contact via **email**
info@banickepoklady.eu

Icons showing individual **categories of "treasure mining" activities** - galleries and museums; tangible heritage; intangible heritage; industrial heritage; events education; for children; hiking; on the map. The individual categories can also be accessed by the platform visitor through the icon on the top bar with the name ACTIVITIES.

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After clicking on the icons representing individual **categories of activities** - galleries and museums; material heritage; intangible heritage; industrial heritage; events; education; for children; hiking; on the map - a menu with activities will appear. You will also see a map with activities marked with **color-coded pins**. The color of the pins depends on the category in which the activities are classified.

You can use a filter to select the location - Banská Bystrica and Banská Štiavnica. It is also possible to change the activity category with a simple click.

Individual activities are identified by name and cover photo. There is also information about the entrance fee and the length of the track that the visitor takes during the visit to the activity.

After clicking on the **route** (trasy) button on the top bar, a map with the Barbara and Fugger routes will be displayed. The map also shows activities marked with pins.

Here, the visitor will also find basic information about the Barbara and Fugger routes with links to the partner organizations that manage them.

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After clicking on the **city** button (Banská Bystrica, Banská Štiavnica) on the top bar, a map with all activities in the city and its surroundings will appear again. Activities are marked with colored pins according to the category of activity.

Banská Štiavnica

Banská Štiavnica sa nachádza v južnej časti Stredného Slovenska v Chránenej krajinskej oblasti Štiavnické vrchy (Slovenské stredohorje). Bývalé banícke mesto Banská Štiavnica je jedným z najkrajších a historicky najzaujímavejších miest na Slovensku. Ťažba drahých kovov v centrálnej časti Štiavnických vrchov má veľmi dlhú históriu. Už v listine z roku 1156 sa táto oblasť spomína ako terra banensium, čiže zem baníkov. Medzi ťažnými nerastmi prevládala strieborná ruda, a preto sa Banská Štiavnica označovala aj ako „srebrné mesto“. V 18. storočí sa Banská Štiavnica stala najväčším centrom ťažby drahých kovov v habsburskej monarchii. V období rokov 1790 až 1863 vydala štedrá zem pod Štiavnickými vrchmi 490 t striebra a 11 t zlata. Postupne sa tu sústredilo aj banícke školstvo a

Here, the visitor will also find basic information about the Banská Bystrica or Banská Štiavnica with link to the website of the city.

In the "body" of the website there are **editorial tips** on the **most visited "Mining treasures of central Slovakia"** and tips on **hiking with the HIKEMATES community**.

In the "footer" of the website are the **logos of the parterres** with whom we cooperate as part of the pilot project. Partner logos are linked to their websites.

There is also the project designation: INCULTUM project 2021-2024 is financed by the H2020 program of the European Union under Grant Agreement n. 101004552

Annex 2 Participatory approach of platform content creation

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The introduction contains basic information about the activity - route length, time required and entrance fees.

With the "on the map" button, the platform visitor can view the activity on the map, according to the uploaded coordinates.

The gallery contains min. 2 photos of the activity. If photos of activities from professional photographers are available, they are also added to the gallery. All photos have their own author, whose name is listed below the photo. In the case of professional as well as amateur photographers who have their own website, this one is linked.

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Below the gallery is the main text about the activity, which includes basic introductory information, extended information, and often interesting facts about the activity.

This section includes important information for the visitor, such as location, entrance fee also with link, time required, opening hours with link, restrictions, parking options, link to the website (if the activity has one), coordinates.

The activity can be **displayed on the map** based on the coordinates. In case the activity consists of several parts, such as Calvary in Banská Štiavnica with 24 stops - these are separately described and shown on the map.

